

MICROSTRUCTURAL EVALUATION OF CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY A SOL-GEL PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Microstructural studies of two fibre-reinforced ceramic matrix composites are described. The first composite contained amorphous silica and glass-ceramic filler particles, whilst the other contained amorphous silica and quartz. Microstructural studies showed that XQCF01 crystallised extensively during sintering and this was accompanied by matrix cracking, whereas HCCF01 had remained mainly amorphous and showed much less cracking. It was concluded that the addition of crystalline fillers to a sol-gel matrix caused large scale crystallisation and shrinkage on cooling, whereas the use of amorphous and semi-crystalline fillers did not.

Keywords: ceramic matrix composite, sol-gel, microstructure.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years much interest has been shown in the reinforcement of ceramic materials so as to impart improved strength and toughness to these traditionally brittle materials. Such composites have commonly been fabricated by hot-pressing routes (1) but there is a growing interest in applying sol-gel fabrication techniques to form composite shapes. Here two composite systems are studied which were formed using sol-gel technology (2), and the effect of fabrication parameters on the microstructure is assessed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The reinforcements were Toray T300 continuous carbon fibres of mean diameter 8 μ m. The composites were made by a filament winding process in which the fibre is taken through a slurry, wound on a drum so as to give unidirectional alignment, freeze-gelled, and sintered at 1100°C. The first composite material, designated HCCF01, was produced using a slurry consisting of colloidal silica (HT50), and particulate fillers of amorphous silica and glass-ceramic (CMA6). The second composite, designated XQCF01, utilised a different type of colloidal silica (X30) in the slurry and quartz replaced the glass-ceramic in the filler.

2.2 Procedure

Samples of composite in the as-manufactured condition were prepared for microstructural examination as follows. A sample of each was ground into a fine powder for x-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, as was a sample of the carbon fibre. Transverse sections of composite were mounted in cold curing epoxy resin for scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Due to the porous nature of the composites, infiltration under vacuum and curing under pressure were used to force

the mounting resin into the pores. Surface preparation of the samples was carried out by grinding on 320 grit silicon carbide paper, followed by polishing with 9 μ m diamond paste and then a 1 μ m diamond and silica suspension. The specimens were finally sputtered with a thin layer of gold.

Thin sections for transmission electron microscopy (TEM) were prepared by first cutting 3mm discs from the bulk composite using a diamond-tipped coring drill and grinding them to approximately 300 μ m thickness on 400 grit SiC paper. The discs were next 'dimpled' on a VCR model D500 Dimpler to give a central specimen thickness of ~50 μ m. Final thinning was carried out by ion milling in a Gatan Duomill.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Carbon fibre

The XRD data from the carbon fibre, Fig 1, show diffuse peaks which correlate with the 100 and 101 diffractions from graphite. The diffuse nature of the peaks suggests that the carbon fibre is not highly graphitised and that there is no long-range crystal order.

3.2 HCCF01

XRD data are shown in Fig 2. The relatively high background level indicates that the composite contains appreciable amorphous material which is attributed to colloidal silica and to carbon fibre. Two crystalline phases were identified, anorthite ($\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$), the corresponding peaks labelled 'A', and α -cristobalite (SiO_2), labelled 'C'. The anorthite is considered to be a constituent of the glass-ceramic filler, whilst the cristobalite has been formed during crystallisation of colloidal silica and/or filler particles during sintering.

Fig 3a, an SEM micrograph, shows that the fibres essentially remain in their original tows and that appreciable porosity is present. The large particle contains cracking and energy-dispersive spectrometry (EDS) showed that it was silica, see Fig 3b. Fig 3c, taken at higher magnification, reveals three phases in addition to the fibre. The light phase (P1), which formed approximately 50% of the material, was found to contain silicon, oxygen, aluminium, magnesium and titanium, see Fig 3d (the gold peak originates from the sputter coating). The darker phase (P2) consists of silicon and oxygen. The third phase (P3) is more difficult to distinguish in the micrograph; EDS confirmed that it contained silicon and oxygen, suggesting that it is colloidal silica.

The phase P3 is shown at higher magnification in the TEM picture, Fig 4a. The corresponding selected area electron diffraction (SAD), Fig 4b, shows it to be amorphous and confirms that it is colloidal silica. The large particle corresponds to phase P1 and is seen to have a duplex structure with the central core containing small lath-like particles 100-200nm long. Phase P1 was found to consist of both crystalline and amorphous material

The interface between the carbon fibre and P1(glass-ceramic) and P3(colloidal silica) is shown in Fig 5. There is evidence of debonding between fibre and P3 phase, although it is not clear whether this is due to weakness in the original composite or a thinning artefact.

3.3 XQCF01

XRD data, Fig 6, shows that the material is mostly α -quartz (peaks labelled 'Q') and α -cristobalite (C). There is little amorphous material present apart from the carbon fibre.

SEM, Fig 7, shows that again that fibres have remained in their original tows. Cracking of the matrix is extensive and there is considerable porosity. However, it was not possible to distinguish between quartz and cristobalite due to their similar mean atomic number.

A TEM picture, Fig 8a, shows the two matrix phases, SAD revealing that the upper phase is quartz, see Fig 8b, and the lower phase is cristobalite, see Fig 8c. There is evidence of strain in the structure, with twins in the cristobalite and strain bands present in both phases.

4 DISCUSSION

Both composite materials contained uneven distributions of carbon fibre and high volumes of porosity. In the case of HCCF01, this is mainly directional, dendritic-type porosity formed during freeze gelation, whereas in XQCF01 there are large amounts of shrinkage cracking in matrix-rich regions. The reasons for this difference can be explained by considering the microstructure of the two composites.

HCCF01 contained α -cristobalite and anorthite. Cristobalite is considered to have been formed by crystallisation and growth of some of the silica filler particles during sintering, whilst the anorthite phase is thought to be associated with the lath-like crystalline phase in the glass-ceramic filler particles. The trace of titanium found in these particles is probably from a TiO_2 nucleating agent which is traditionally used to nucleate anorthite (3). The most important phase, however, is the colloidal silica. In HCCF01 it has clearly not fully densified during sintering, and the original silica spheres are still visible. This means that any thermal stresses set up during cooling can be accommodated in the matrix, and no additional cracking occurs.

In XQCF01 this is not the case. The colloidal silica has almost completely crystallised during sintering to form cristobalite. Initially this cristobalite will be the high temperature β -phase, and the matrix will be fully dense. During cooling there will be strains set up in the matrix due to the thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between cristobalite and the quartz filler, and also because of the 4% volume change when β -cristobalite transforms to the low temperature α -phase. Some of the strain is relieved by twinning, but the majority is released by extensive matrix cracking.

The much higher degree of matrix crystallisation in XQCF01 could be due to two reasons. Either the different silica sol (X30) used has a greater tendency to crystallise under the fabrication conditions used, or that the crystalline nature of the quartz filler gives more impetus to crystal growth than either the amorphous silica or semi-crystalline CMA6 fillers used in HCCF01. It is considered that this latter explanation is more likely.

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Fig 1 XRD curve for ground Toray T300 carbon fibre

Fig 2 XRD curve for ground HCCF01 composite

Fig 3a Polished section, composite HCCF01, backscattered electron image

Fig 3b EDS of large particle

Fig 3c As Fig 3a, higher magnification

Fig 3d EDS of particle P1

Fig 4a TEM of HCCF01 matrix, showing P1 particle in P3 region

Fig 4b SAD of P3 region

Fig 5 TEM of fibre/matrix interface in HCCF01

Fig 6 XRD of ground composite XQCF01

Fig 7 Polished section, composite XQCF01, backscattered electron image

Fig 8a TEM of XQCF01 matrix, showing quartz filler (Q) in cristobalite (C)

Fig 8b SAD of quartz particle

Fig 8c SAD of cristobalite